

eDNAAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Proceedings of the WP3 workshop for conceptualising and writing on the eDNA data ecosystem

5 February 2025

Milestone 6

Work Package 3

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring
Milestone title	Proceedings of the WP3 workshop for conceptualising and writing on the eDNA data ecosystem
Milestone number	6
Work package title	Data Standards, Data Linking, & Compatibility
Work package number	3
Lead beneficiary	UNESCO, EMBL-EBI
Author(s)	Emilie Boulanger, Camila Babo, Joana Verissimo, Frédéric Rimet, Katrina Exter, Peter Woollard + the other participants who all contributed during the workshop
Due date	28 February 2025
Submission date	28 February 2025
Dissemination level	Public

Executive Summary

The eDNAqua-Plan WP3 workshop, held on the 5th of February 2025, brought together eDNA experts and stakeholders to conceptualize and improve the eDNA data ecosystem. Participants examined the current landscape of reference libraries, eDNA data publishing, and biodiversity databases, identifying key challenges such as metadata inconsistencies, limited taxonomic curation, and fragmented data flows. For reference libraries, the need for common taxonomic curation principles and a core set of essential metadata were emphasized. For eDNA data publishing, a set of common controlled vocabulary (particularly bioinformatics), better data submission and handling guidelines are needed. Overall, data and metadata flows need to be improved, with tailored approaches for research and national monitoring need to be considered.

Looking ahead, participants envisioned an ideal eDNA ecosystem comprising a network of taxonomically curated reference libraries, accessible via a centralized data portal. Recommendations included promoting standardised metadata practices, developing accreditation frameworks for reference databases, training stakeholders in FAIR principles and fostering stronger links between research and national monitoring initiatives. The workshop also emphasised reducing ecosystem fragmentation by consolidating standards and implementing quality-control schemas for data fitness. The workshop outcomes will inform WP3's Deliverables, Milestone M3.3 and support WP5's blueprint and roadmap for future system implementation. In this way it will contribute to shaping a more efficient and FAIR eDNA data ecosystem and ultimately support the advancement of biodiversity monitoring across Europe.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
BIN	Barcode Index Numbers
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BOLD	The Barcode of Life Data Systems
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DwC	Darwin Core
EC	European Commission
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
iBOL	International Barcode of Life
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MAG	Metagenome Assembled Genome
MDT	Metabarcoding Data Toolkit
MixS	Minimum Information about any Sequence
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OA	Open Access
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
SBDI	Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SSBE	Seascape Belgium

SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen Ympäristökeskus
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (previously Taxonomic Databases Working Group)
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WP	Work Package(s)

Introduction

The WP3 Workshop for conceptualising and writing on the eDNA data ecosystem (eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 3.2) took place online on Wednesday 5th of February 2025. The goal of the workshop was to conceptualise the eDNA data ecosystem in Europe at different levels (or “layers”) covering reference libraries (Task 3.1), eDNA data publishing (Task 3.2), biodiversity databases and biobanks (both Task 3.3). Firstly, we reviewed the current landscape considering the different databases and repositories, data flows between them, metadata requirements, standards and taxonomies used for each layer. Next, we envisioned the ideal future of this landscape which would improve access and reusability of eDNA-related data, and identified ways to achieve that future. The workshop brought together eDNAqua-Plan members of Task 3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 as well as members of Work Package 4 and WP5 and a few external contributors. In total, 22 eDNA (data) scientists, practitioners and stakeholders actively participated. The following proceedings recount the landscape representations that were prepared up front as well as the comments, discussions and ideas that occurred throughout the workshop day. These materials will feed into the different WP3 discussions and deliverables and the next upcoming milestone M3.3 “First version of digital ecosystem landscape proposal”. The materials will also provide early input for WP5’s T5.1 Blueprint for future system(s)/workflow(s) and T5.2: Roadmap implementation.

Attendance

Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO, WP3), Peter Woollard (EMBL-EBI, WP3), Saara Suominen (UNESCO, WP3), Frederic Rimet (INRAE, WP3), Ian Probert (SU, WP3), Filipe Costa (UMINHO, WP3), Camila Babo (BIOPOLIS-CIBIO, WP3), Joana Verissimo (BIOPOLIS-CIBIO, WP3), Katrina Exter (VLIZ, WP3), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ, WP5), Antonio Camacho (UVEG, WP3), Antonio Picazo (UVEG, WP3), Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC, WP3), Kristian Meissner (SYKE, WP2), Veera Norros (SYKE, WP2), Tiina Laamanen (SYKE, WP2), Sofie Derycke (ILVO, WP4), Florian Leese (UDE, WP4), Arne Beermann (UDE, WP4), Tim Collart (SSBE, WP5), Tobias Guldborg Frøslev (GBIF, external), Maria Kahlert (SLU, external)

Methodology

Because the goal of this workshop was to discuss the state of the current landscape and conceptualise the future one, each task was asked to prepare a visual representation of their respective landscape up front. These visual representations or diagrams would constitute the different “layers” of the overall landscape, and serve as the basis for discussion during the workshop. The first layer was dedicated to the landscape of genetic reference libraries (Task 3.1), the second layer was dedicated to the data repositories and publishing practices along the steps of an eDNA workflow (Task 3.2) and the third and final layer was dedicated to the biodiversity data publishers and biobanks (Task 3.3). The workshop day was separated into two major sessions in order to first discuss the current landscape of each layer (morning session), and then to conceptualise their respective future landscapes (afternoon session) (Table 1).

To best guide both the discussions and the overall course of the workshop, a virtual working space was prepared in advance. This was done on the online platform Miro (miro.com). The working space was separated into different sections corresponding to each of the sessions and landscape layers. These sections contained a space to deposit the landscape diagrams that were prepared up-front. Alongside them, a few questions were prepared to guide the discussion and participants could add sticky notes with their comments and ideas. These were combined with verbal feedback which led to efficient and interactive discussions amongst all participants. The final export of the Miro board containing the

diagrams, questions, answers and notes can be found in high resolution in the proceedings' Appendix 1.

Table 1. Schedule of the workshop day.

Time (CET)	Topic	
9:30-09:50	Introduction + Miro demo	WP3 leads
09:50-10:20	Current landscape - T3.1	T3.1 lead & all participate
10:20-10:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobreak 	
10:30-11:00	Current landscape - T3.2	T3.2 lead & all
11:00-11:45	Current landscape - T3.3	T3.3 lead & all
11:45-12:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobreak 	
12:00-12:30	What can be linked between the maps?	All
12:30-13:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lunch break 	
13:30-14:15	Future landscape - T3.1	T3.1 lead & all
14:15-15:00	Future landscape - T3.2	T3.2 lead & all
15:00-15:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biobreak 	
15:15-16:00	Future landscape - T3.3	T3.3 lead & all
16:00-17:00	Putting it all together	All

Morning session: introduction & current landscapes

The morning started with a short introduction to how the day will go and how the virtual environment works. Because a lot of the terms we use might be interpreted differently, participants were asked to contribute to the definition of these terms. Each task was then given time to present their diagram of the current landscape at the level of either the reference libraries (T3.1), the eDNA data publishing (T3.2), and the surrounding ecosystem of biodiversity publishers and biobanks (T3.3). These diagrams were discussed in detail guided by questions on which databases or repositories are represented as nodes, which links should be represented, what (meta)data information should be portrayed, but also the way in which the different information can be portrayed. The structure of the landscapes were discussed as well, questioning what works well, what doesn't, what are the risks and what should be improved.

Afternoon session: future landscape & putting it all together

In the afternoon, we discussed and mapped our vision of the future, ideal digital landscapes and defined steps of how to get there. These discussions were based on the annotated diagrams of the current landscape from the morning sessions, and were guided by the following key questions:

- What is our vision of success?
- What would an ideal landscape then look like?
- What activities or tools need to be implemented to get there?
- How or by whom could these be implemented?

Finally, we had allocated time at the end of the day to put all the work together. This time slot was also used to go over any comments or aspects of the landscape that couldn't be addressed in the earlier sessions.

Definitions

A few definitions were discussed at the start of the workshop which will provide a working basis for us to iterate over and refine as the project progresses (Table 2). The list is however short and it was suggested that all the necessary terms from the landscape drafts will need to be defined. These include a.o. sample metadata, study metadata, raw sequence data, processed sequence data, standard, sequence repository and curation.

Table 2. Definition of a few core terms relevant to the eDNA data ecosystem. More will be added as the project progresses.

Term	Definition
Data(set)	Digital object(s) that are the results of the experiment/activity
Metadata	Metadata contained in datasets that describe the experiment, the environment, the activity
Catalogue metadata	Metadata that describes datasets held by some dataset catalogue, provided as a separate digital object to the data
Provenance metadata	The metadata specifically to describe who, what, where, when and how of the activities that led to a sample or a dataset
Occurrence	The existence of an organism (at a place and time)
Reference library	The reference (data) that was used to derive some result (for us, taxon classifications) via a (programmatic) comparison

Table 3. Definition of Resource terms relevant to the eDNA data ecosystem.

Resource term	Description	URL
Algaebase	A database of information on algae, including terrestrial, marine, and freshwater organisms, providing taxonomic, distributional, and ecological data.	https://www.algaebase.org/
BODC	The British Oceanographic Data Centre provides a comprehensive range of marine data services, including data management, quality control, and dissemination of oceanographic and marine data.	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/
CHEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest is a freely available dictionary of molecular entities focused on 'small' chemical compounds, providing standardized information about their structures and biological roles.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/
DASSH	The Archive for Marine Species and Habitats Data serves as the UK's national repository for marine biodiversity data, ensuring long-term curation and accessibility of marine	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/

Resource term	Description	URL
	species and habitat information.	
DataONE	A distributed framework and sustainable cyberinfrastructure providing open, persistent, robust, and secure access to well-described and easily discovered Earth observational data.	https://www.dataone.org/
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan is a biological database that collects DNA sequences, functioning as a member of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration alongside ENA and GenBank.	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/
DwC	Darwin Core is a standard designed to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing a stable framework for biodiversity data.	https://dwc.tdwg.org/
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network: A network of organizations supported by the EU's integrated maritime policy, providing access to marine data across various themes, including bathymetry, biology, chemistry, geology, human activities, physics, and seabed habitats.	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive: A comprehensive database of nucleotide sequences from the European Bioinformatics Institute, offering open access to sequence data for the scientific community.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
ENVO	The Environment Ontology offers a controlled vocabulary for the environments in which biological entities live, supporting the consistent annotation of environmental data across various domains.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/envo
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biogeographic Information System: An online marine biogeographic database compiling data on all living marine creatures, aiming to centralize scattered biogeographic data collected by European institutions and make them freely accessible.	https://www.eurobis.org/
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility: An international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments, providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.	https://www.gbif.org/
GEOBON	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network: A global network aiming to improve the acquisition, coordination, and delivery of biodiversity observations and related services to users.	https://geobon.org/
GEOSS	The Global Earth Observation System of Systems aims to connect existing Earth observation systems worldwide to promote collaboration and data sharing for informed decision-making.	https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php
GFBio	The German Federation for Biological Data offers a sustainable, service-oriented infrastructure for biological and environmental research data, supporting data archiving,	https://www.gfbio.org/

Resource term	Description	URL
	management, and sharing.	
GTDB	The Genome Taxonomy Database provides a standardized microbial genome taxonomy based on genome phylogeny, aiding in the consistent classification of bacterial and archaeal genomes.	https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/
IBOL	The International Barcode of Life project aims to establish a globally accessible DNA barcode reference library, enhancing the ability to identify and discover species.	https://ibol.org/
IMOS	Integrated Marine Observing System: An Australian national collaborative research infrastructure delivering ocean observations to support marine and climate science.	https://imos.org.au/
INSDC	The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) archives nucleotide sequence data, from raw to assembled and annotated sequences, from around the world. Current members of INSDC are NCBI GenBank, DDBJ and ENA.	https://www.insdc.org/
INSPIRE	The Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community aims to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure, facilitating the sharing of environmental spatial information among public sector organizations.	https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/
ITIS	The Integrated Taxonomic Information System provides authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes, supporting consistent naming and classification across databases.	https://www.itis.gov/
MARBEF	Marine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning was a network of excellence integrating and disseminating knowledge on marine biodiversity, now serving as a legacy website with access to data and publications.	http://www.marbef.org/
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network: A global initiative to monitor and report on the status and trends of marine biodiversity to support conservation and sustainable use of ocean resources.	https://marinebon.org/
MGNify	A resource developed by EMBL-EBI that offers an automated pipeline for the analysis and archiving of microbiome data, aiding in the understanding of microbial communities.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/
MITOFISH	A comprehensive database of fish mitochondrial genomes, providing valuable information for studies in phylogenetics, population genetics, and species identification.	http://mitofish.aori.u-tokyo.ac.jp/
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information: A U.S. government agency that provides access to biomedical and genomic information, including the GenBank DNA sequence database.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System: A global open-access	https://obis.org/

Resource term	Description	URL
	data and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity for science, conservation, and sustainable development.	
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System: A system under development by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, aiming to integrate existing ocean data and information systems into a collaborative, web-based network	https://www.iode.org/
OpenARIS	Open Access to Research Infrastructure in the South Caucasus and Central Asia aims to enhance the accessibility and visibility of research infrastructures in these regions.	https://www.openaris.com/
OTN	Ocean Tracking Network: A global research and technology platform tracking aquatic animals to understand their movements, habitats, and survival in the face of changing ocean environments.	https://oceantrackingnetwork.org/
PANGEA	Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science: An open-access library for archiving, publishing, and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research, covering fields like oceanography, geology, and environmental sciences	https://www.pangaea.de/
PlutoF	A cloud-based platform providing services for managing and publishing biodiversity data, supporting taxonomic, ecological, and genomic research.	https://plutof.ut.ee/
PR2	The Protist Ribosomal Reference database offers curated sequences of protist ribosomal RNA genes, supporting ecological and evolutionary studies of protists.	https://pr2-database.org/
QUOT	The QUOT project focuses on the quantification of ocean transport, aiming to improve the understanding of ocean circulation and its impact on climate.	https://www.quot.org/
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards: An international organization that develops and promotes standards for the exchange of biological/biodiversity data to support the wider global community.	https://www.tdwg.org/
UNITE	A database providing molecular identification of fungi, offering a comprehensive resource for DNA-based identification and classification of fungal species.	https://unite.ut.ee/
World Data System and World Radiation Monitoring Centre	The World Data System supports universal and equitable access to quality-assured scientific data, while the World Ozone and Ultraviolet Radiation Data Centre (WOUDC) archives global ozone and UV radiation data.	https://woudc.org/
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species: An authoritative and comprehensive list of names of marine organisms, aiming to provide the most accurate and up-to-date taxonomic information.	https://www.marinespecies.org/

Layer 1 - Reference databases - Task 3.1

Current Landscape

What we presented:

We presented the current landscape of genetic reference libraries in a conceptual manner. The current landscape can be seen in different – hierarchical - layers, from the broad/primary nucleotide databases where data is generally published and harvested, down to quality-controlled and taxonomically curated reference libraries typically specialised in one or more taxonomic groups. We thus represented the landscape as Russian dolls:

1. The outer & largest layer – or doll – consists of the primary nucleotide databases. The most important ones are the EMBL-EBI European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the NCBI GenBank. Together with the DNA DataBase of Japan they continuously share all their data through the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC).
2. The middle layer consists of databases where data undergo quality control by checking the availability of metadata. The nucleotide sequences are either harvested from the primary nucleotide databases above, or newly published. An important one here is the BOLD database. The BOLD database both harvests data from NCBI, and allows publishing new nucleotide sequences through their portal to NCBI.
3. The inner layer consists of specialised libraries typically focusing on certain taxonomic groups and that have conducted taxonomic curation of their sequence data. Taxonomic curation consists of checking that neighbor sequences share homogeneous taxonomic names (by using phylogenetic tools, by checking taxonomic synonyms, by checking recent publications). This taxonomic curation is typically not reported back to the primary databases where sequence data was harvested from, with the exception of the feedback loop of annotations from the UNITE community to EMBL-EBI through the ELIXIR Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH)¹.

Two additional layers were added to the database representation for discussion: one focusing on the taxonomic references used by each database or by sequence data providers (Figure 2a) and one focusing on the metadata requirements by each database (Figure 2b). This initial representation of the reference database landscape is largely based on the WP2 Task 2.1 landscape analysis, as well as the WP4 Milestone 4.2 report and discussions within the WP3 Task 3.1 group. The reference taxonomies and metadata requirements of databases were taken from the Task 2.1 manual search results as reported in the Deliverable 2.1 Appendix 3. The reference taxonomies used by sequence data providers were taken from the Task 2.1 survey as reported in the Deliverable 2.1 Table 8, and the mandatory metadata requested by databases (BOLD and MycoDiversity Database MDD) were taken from the Deliverable 2.1 Table 18.

¹ <https://unite.ut.ee/curation.php>

Figure 1. Initial representation of the current reference database landscape as hierarchical "Russian dolls". Reference databases can generally be classified into three categories with different levels of quality-control and taxonomic curation. Data publishing is typically done at the higher level (generalist nucleotide databases) and data harvest is typically done from top to bottom. However, some feedback loops and alternate data submission paths exist.

Figure 2. Initial representation of the reference database landscape from Figure 1, with an additional layer representing the taxonomic references used by each database (top, yellow) and one representing the metadata recommendations and mandatory metadata reported for the different reference databases (bottom, red).

Finally, an attempt was made to represent the landscape for archiving and reusing reference genomes, although much of this needs more investigation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Attempted representation of the reference database landscape for genomes.

Major feedback and suggestions:

Comments leading to discussions were either made on the way the landscape was represented, or on the state of the current landscape. The following comments were raised and discussed:

The categorisation of libraries needs to be revised. There are different levels of quality control and curation possible and employed by the different libraries. E.g. verifying the quality of sequences, verifying if metadata is available, whether the taxonomic names are valid, and verifying the accuracy of the taxonomic identification (= taxonomic curation) which is possible to different levels. Some of the databases conduct only quality control, others conduct curation to different extents. This should be further investigated and better represented in the figure. The use of the term “curation” should also be well defined (e.g. meaning that genetic neighbours need to have the same name). Some information to take into account are that Genbank does some taxonomy checks when you upload sequence data, BOLD hosts taxonomically curated sequences, and COInr does not curate taxonomy. This classification work is ongoing by Task 2.1 for the writing of their paper.

Several databases were noted to be missing. These were: Cydrasil (cyanobacteria Database, <https://www.cydrasil.org/>), the Eukaryome database (18S,ITS,28S for all eukaryotes, <https://eukaryome.org/>), and the National Microbiome Data Collaborative (NMMC, <https://microbiomedata.org/>). Similarly, for reference genomes, it was noted that MAGs are relevant for Bacteria and Archaea, but if they are to be considered, then the SeqCode registry (<https://registry.seqco.de>) should be also included somewhere. And MGnify should not be under the quality-controlled database box, as it's an analysis platform and there is (currently) no direct way for users to submit their own processed data to MGnify. It does contain MAG catalogues which (in the future) will also include Eukaryotic MAGs². Overall, the discussions were focused on genetic reference databases and less so on genomic reference databases.

It looks like curated databases harvest from quality-controlled databases, which is not the case usually (they harvest directly from Genbank etc). These data flows should be better represented. We should also capture the links to the culture collections, both in & out. Database tools exist for linking between collections. E.g. BioSamples allows linking to voucher specimens in biobanks. Some museum collections are thinking of creating DOIs for each specimen. However the goal is not to represent all data flows but focus on the most important ones. We should be careful not to lose the overall landscape with too many details.

It currently looks as if only two libraries care about metadata. But others also have metadata and all the libraries do have a core set of shared metadata. This could be something good to add as a layer, and from there we contribute our recommendations of essential metadata for taxonomic curation. The metadata recommendations will mostly be valid for the systems where data is deposited. The metadata in the lower-end databases then often depends on the metadata that is provided by the higher levels. From these, the databases choose a set of metadata, and there exists a set of common metadata that all - or most - libraries share. Our work should focus on understanding what that common set consists of, and make recommendations on what metadata that common set should include.

² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/browse/genomes>

Similarly, the hierarchical structure of the data trail means that the quality on the lower end of the landscape (i.e. in the smallest dolls) depends on the quality of the input at the higher end. The quality of the sequence data that enters the system though e.g. ENA and GenBank thus have a lot of responsibility. We could envision quality flags or quality stars which would rate the quality of the metadata (e.g. having sufficient provenance) and/or the quality of curation. A FAIR/quality-grading system could then be developed.

Metadata which provides the provenance of the sequence (from wet to dry) should be recommended. Each repository should hold its part of this provenance metadata in such a way, that it can be referred back to by others. We should recommend (1) the content of each provenance metadata object and (2) how to provide these digital objects so they can be linked to.

Databases should allow (and accommodate) user (and/or community) curation. Participants have found several small errors in ENA samples and studies that could be very easily corrected. The ELIXIR Clearinghouse could be a solution to allow these user-corrections.

There is a need for better guidance on how to fill in metadata so that terms are uniform. Data providers still don't know how to accurately document the sample metadata during submission to databases like ENA. Detailed tutorials or accessible guidelines should be developed.

Future landscape

What we presented:

Instead of presenting a prepared concept of the future landscape, we gathered ideas from the participants to conceptualise this future together. We started from the base figure of the current landscape presented in the beginning of the workshop, and discussed what our vision of success would be and how we could get there.

Major feedback and suggestions:

The vision for a **successful future landscape** of reference libraries was focused around the importance of taxonomic curation and the use of **taxonomically curated databases** for taxonomic annotation, and **centralising access** to quality-controlled and taxonomically curated sequences. Creating one large, taxonomically-curated eDNA reference database of aquatic organisms of Europe was not deemed feasible nor necessary or desirable. Each of the current curated databases are created and maintained by different groups or institutions and each of these databases have their own focus, specialisation, taxonomic specialists and management. This diversity in existing databases should be maintained.

Instead, the (ideal) future landscape would consist of independently curated and maintained databases/libraries which follow common, guiding principles and are accessible through a central portal. The reference databases/libraries undergo a curation of metadata, taxonomic name validation but also taxonomic accuracy to ensure reliable taxonomic assignment. This

curation would create feedback that goes back to the data providers, especially correcting taxonomic assignment errors.

To achieve this future landscape, our recommendations would follow these steps:

1. Define and recommend common curation principles
2. Recommend essential metadata to allow for quality-control and curation (and thus establish the reliability of the taxonomic assignment later on)
3. Create a recognition or accreditation system of databases/libraries that follow these recommendations
 - a. This could help databases get funding to be sustainable. The lack of long term funding for the curation of reference databases is a problem. We could envision a certification at the EU level where the curation of reference databases is recognised as strategically important, and databases get recognised as following the EU-level curation requirements. Such certification or label could help in getting national funding. The Global Biodata Coalition (<https://globalbiodata.org>) was cited as an organisation that does this globally.
4. Create a data portal that centralises access to these recognised databases that adhere to a set of curation principles. This platform would give access to a registry of trusted reference libraries. This centralisation approach would maintain the diversity in existing databases, while ensuring common curation requirements are met for reliability.
 - a. As an example: this manually-curated European marine NIS library is available as a BOLD dataset. If there was a portal aggregating curated records for eDNA-based aquatic monitoring in Europe these different libraries could be linked up there: <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15020174>
 - b. iBOL Europe, which is gaining a lot of momentum, could be a potential central hub for this.
 - c. From a monitoring perspective, such a portal should allow us to easily extract reliable sequences with curated taxonomy from species from a particular area based on a species list of that area.
 - d. In order to create a unified reference library, we should also focus on mappings between the standards used in different existing libraries, so that a unified library can be extracted as part of a workflow (allowing to select which sources to be included based on the scientific question).
5. Establish a feedback system from curators and users back to the data providers in primary platforms.
 - a. Currently, records in the primary databases are meant to be an archival copy. The ELIXIR clearing house however allows to add annotations to ENA which are shown alongside the archived one.

In parallel, a set of best-practice principles or recommendations should be set. These include our metadata recommendations, as well as recommendations on tracking sequence and assignment provenance to a.o. avoid artificially inflating biodiversity. By always linking taxonomic assignment to the original sequence in research data portals, we avoid “biodiversity entropy” which is caused by different taxonomic assignments of the same source data which is then uploaded to data research databases. RO-Crate (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>) could be a solution.

Another expected key outcome from our work would be to contribute to the taxonomic community (experts who identify, name, describe, and classify biodiversity working from the level of molecules, including eDNA and eRNA, genomes and metagenomes, species and populations, to habitats and ecosystems), and ensure that its capacity to engage with and support policy and other decision-making are strengthened. Again, iBOL-Europe was cited here alongside the upcoming call HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-03: Strengthening taxonomic approaches for biodiversity.

Summary

The current landscape of genetic reference libraries was presented using a hierarchical model or “Russian dolls”. The outermost layer comprises primary nucleotide databases such as ENA and GenBank, which continuously share data through the INSDC. The middle layer included databases that apply minimum quality control measures, such as BOLD. The innermost layer consisted of specialised, taxonomically curated libraries. Additional layers included the taxonomic references used by the different databases and their metadata requirements. In this presentation of the current landscape, the categorisation of the different reference libraries will need to be refined based on the different levels of quality-control and taxonomic curation. The core set of metadata shared by the different reference libraries will also be reviewed and will help us identify and recommend a set of essential metadata.

Based on this initial representation, a vision for an ideal future was discussed which should consist of an interconnected network of **taxonomically curated reference libraries**. These should follow **common curation principles** and be accessible through a **centralised data portal**. This would allow for accreditation mechanisms and feedback systems to relay curation and corrections back to the data providers.

To achieve this future landscape, our recommendations would follow concrete steps:

1. Define and recommend common curation principles
2. Recommend essential metadata to allow for quality-control and curation
3. Create an accreditation system of libraries that follow these recommendations
4. Create a data portal that centralises access to the accredited databases
5. Establish a feedback system

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repositories to ensure proper documentation. Once collected, the samples undergo laboratory processing, where DNA extraction, amplification, and sequencing occur. The raw sequencing data, written in FASTQ format, is then subject to quality filtering, generating processed data in FASTQ or FASTA. This data undergoes bioinformatics analysis, which is highly variant across different research aims and users but usually includes additional filtering procedures and clustering to generate processed sequence data in FASTA. This data, particularly the raw and quality filtering sequencing data, is then submitted to sequence-specific repositories, such as EMBL-ENA, NCBI SRA, and DDBJ, or broad-scope repositories, such as Zenodo and Dryad, where it is archived for future use.

The processed sequencing data and relevant metadata are then submitted to taxonomic assignment workflows, allowing species identification from eDNA samples. The resulting data is crucial for downstream applications, including biodiversity monitoring and environmental assessments. Tools like MGnify (for microorganisms) facilitate automated taxonomic and functional sequence analysis, while ELIXIR's clearinghouse supports community-driven metadata curation. This perspective ensures that metadata sharing remains a key part of scientific communication.

Occurrence data records a specific species observed at a particular time and place. In this diagram, occurrence data is solely derived from processed sequencing information. Once the taxonomic identification is complete, eDNA-based occurrence data is formatted for integration into biodiversity occurrence databases. This data is archived in international repositories such as GBIF, NCBI TLS, or OBIS, ensuring accessibility. National and institutional databases, including FinBIF, the Atlas of Living Australia, and the Swedish ASV Database, can store occurrence data for regional applications. Broad-scope platforms like Zenodo, Dryad, and Figshare are also used.

Major feedback and suggestions:

Regarding missing links and elements, it was pointed out that the metadata repositories present were only in the governance of NCBI, but others also exist. PANGEA, described as a data publisher for earth and environmental science, was suggested as an additional broad-scope repository as it [contained entries with eDNA data](#). One participant recommended adding a link from MGnify to GBIF, as MGnify was previously set as a [GBIF publisher](#), and the data flow was already established.

Regarding national databases, one additional example was the [MVM](#), a Swedish national database for environmental data. The MVM is expanding to include field sampling protocol data and is open access (OA), although it is only available in Swedish. Currently, users can search for sites but not for samples or site IDs, though this feature is under development. Additionally, the MVM is working on integrating ASV and other DNA data. It was also noted that established OA national databases for environmental metadata, such as those used for routine monitoring under the Water Framework Directive (WFD) or Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), already exist in Sweden. These databases focus primarily on monitoring data, not hosting research data. These platforms do not interface with global repositories like NCBI.

Limitations were also pointed out; for example, a participant stated that linking metadata between different platforms is currently somewhat restricted. Metadata should be complete and provided in machine-to-machine formats to improve interoperability.

Participants also noted some inaccurate details, such as the MIxS standard being relevant to all INSDC-encompassing repositories, not only EMBL-ENA. The “No paper link” in some repositories indicates they do not allow an entry directly associated with a DOI or scientific article URL. Some pointed out that ENA studies contemplated a “Claim to ORCID” option, where linking studies to authors was possible and

specifically applicable when a paper wasn't available or registered. Another question was whether the "Taxonomic Assignment" workflow step was correctly positioned, as ASV/OTU tables do not require taxonomic assignment. It was also emphasised that data filtering steps can be applied after taxonomic assignment. However, these steps must always be adequately documented to ensure accurate data reuse and a correct interpretation of results.

Although not yet available, some suggestions of links were planned to be established soon. The first is a link between EurOBIS and EMODnet Biology (<https://www.eurobis.org/emodnet>). EurOBIS will serve as the central hub for making biological data available within EMODnet Biology and provide access to data products. A participant also highlighted that OBIS would soon regularly re-run sequence similarity searches (BLAST) Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) and noted that GBIF might adopt a similar approach quickly.

Building on this point, it was observed that multiple repositories processing data from the same source—such as MGnify and OBIS and GBIF soon BLASTing their OTU/ASV entries—could lead to widespread duplication across platforms, potentially resulting in varying interpretations of the same data. A participant mentioned GBIF's data-clustering feature (<https://data-blog.gbif.org/post/clustering-occurrences/>), which can potentially identify related records within the platform. Features like these could detect duplicate entries and find interesting relationships.

A discussion also occurred regarding submitting ASVs to repositories not specific to sequence data, such as Zenodo. Some participants pointed out that this was the least advantageous solution regarding FAIRness. In contrast, others argued that if submitters followed minimal requirements for metadata standards, the same principles would be followed. The discussion concluded that submitting ASVs to such repositories could pose challenges for FAIRness due to inconsistent metadata standards. Different metadata nomenclatures, such as 'depth(m)' vs 'DEPTH' field names, could create interoperability issues. Consistent metadata standards are crucial for seamless data integration and interoperability across platforms.

A significant point reiterated throughout the discussion was the need for a bioinformatics-controlled vocabulary. The current eDNA landscape lacks a generalised adoption of a standardized set of terms used to describe bioinformatics procedures (workflows) in a consistent and structured way. This is particularly evident in the bioinformatics pipeline, where participants noted a lack of clear minimum requirements for metadata creation. Facilitating information sharing between authors and users on the algorithms, tools, software, and their respective versions would enhance reusability. One participant raised that the Minimum Information for an Omic Protocol (MIOP) could cover this need. The categories present in MIOP can help the user assign relevant omic categories when submitting their protocol to the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) [1].

Additionally, while research applications might have more flexibility, official monitoring requires stringent standards to ensure reliability and acceptance. Private laboratories seeking accreditation for metabarcoding analyses are awaiting ISO standards, highlighting the practical importance of standardisation. Concerns were raised about DwC not being a proper ISO standard and lacking a revision process linked to legislative monitoring. This makes it vulnerable to criticism from those who question molecular methods in regulatory contexts. As such, Darwin Core (DwC) principles were suggested as a foundation for creating an independent ISO standard.

A frequently repeated and valuable suggestion was that most participants emphasised the need for a guided trail outlining the steps and processes, including direction and possible starting points, to assist new users of eDNA data. To this end, FAIRe, a project dedicated to optimising data and metadata

standards while promoting a ready-to-use approach for FAIR eDNA, was highlighted as a key initiative. Their website (<https://fair-edna.github.io/guidelines.html>) provides a comprehensive guideline outlining essential steps, vocabulary, and procedures for users to get familiar with generating FAIR eDNA data.

A participant also noted that the diagram was mainly based on the processing steps of Illumina short-read sequencing. Using other sequencing workflows, such as Nanopore, could require additional steps.

One participant commented that it would be productive to understand whether metadata standards can be sufficiently interoperable. This is intended to be an outcome of Deliverable 3.2.

Future landscape

The second discussion focused on the future vision for the eDNA ecosystem. To represent this, we updated our diagram by refining elements from the previous version. While the overall structure of the diagram remains largely similar, the goal was to encourage the exchange of participants' ideas on what an ideal eDNA ecosystem would look like. Key changes included removing broad-scope repositories for storing sequencing and occurrence data. Given its focus on hosting code, GitHub was retained as the primary code and script storage repository. In contrast, single pipelines can have more adequate archiving solutions.

What we presented:

Figure 5: Diagram illustrating the envisioner eDNA ecosystem for pre and processed data.

Major feedback and suggestions:

Participants reiterated the need for better data submission and handling guides in the second session. A clear plan outlining where users should submit the various types of data generated throughout the eDNA monitoring workflow, such as raw sequence data, processed sequence data, metadata, and occurrence data, is needed. This would help ensure a more consistent and predictable data flow for both eDNA users and data owners. A tracking system would assist users based on their starting points. However, it was noted that there is a wide range of applications and focus on eDNA research, which is also vastly different from the needs of routine monitoring. Additionally, more considerable effort is needed to encourage individuals to submit their data to searchable databases. Some suggested that this information be available on a web portal; others indicated that OBPS's portal could be a good host for promoting adoption.

Again, the solutions and plans being carried out by the Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure (SBDI) (<https://biodiversitydata.se/>) solutions were provided as a positive example to look up to. Their national solution for freshwater eDNA data management aims to create a comprehensive system where researchers can store raw sequence data for reanalysis, deposit generated ASV sequences, record annotated species names with abundance data, include field metadata, document methodological information, and implement data retrieval. While acknowledging the complexity of such a task, even at a national level, SBDI plans to connect with international databases, ensuring raw sequences and ASVs

are uploaded to ENA and SBDI. This exemplifies a practical approach to creating an accessible yet comprehensive data management system.

Several participants highlighted the need for data analysis tools and bioinformatics pipelines to generate results with standardised fields and enable direct uploads to relevant repositories with the appropriate metadata. While widespread adoption may be challenging, introducing such features in some tools could gradually raise standards across the field, ultimately shaping a new paradigm.

To facilitate eDNA data reuse, it was stated that data would require a provenance profile. In the present context, provenance can be described as a digital trail detailing a data object's origin and historical context [2]. In choosing a dataset to answer a scientific question, informing the user regarding the contextual fit and data validity for adequate reuse is essential. There should be a way to persistently flag errors in datasets such as contaminations, inadequate controls, and other errors. This would ensure this information is not lost upon re-analysing sequence data. Data provenance could play a significant role in these situations by facilitating the identification and rectify of inconsistencies and inaccuracies.

Most participants agreed that scientific publishers must ensure authors submit sequencing data according to recognised standards. However, despite most journals mandating the submission of raw sequencing data, many still allowed articles to be published with a “data available upon request” statement without challenging this practice.

A broadly agreed-upon topic was the clear need for institutional data management plans and the respective resources for carrying them out. Participants suggested that there should be a shift in responsibility from users to publishers and repositories. A good outcome of this project could be creating a ready-made eDNA data management plan. An alternative to this was the currently available GBIF/OBIS guide “Publishing DNA-derived data through biodiversity data platforms” (<https://doi.org/10.35035/doc-vf1a-nr22>), which is due for an update where current developments, such as the MDT tool and FAIRe project would be considered.

Summary

The T3.2 discussions focused on analysing and improving the eDNA ecosystem for current and future scenarios. Among the key takeaways were:

- **Data Standards:** A clear need exists for better standardisation, particularly in bioinformatics procedures. The current ecosystem lacks a controlled vocabulary and clear minimum requirements for metadata creation.
- **Repository Integration:** Current limitations include inadequate metadata interoperability between platforms and potential data duplication across repositories. Solutions should improve interoperability through machine-to-machine formats and implement consistent metadata standards across different platforms.
- **Data Quality and Provenance:** Data quality should be maintained through provenance profiles that track data origins and flag potential errors or contamination. This system would ensure proper data reuse and validation across different studies and applications.
- **Institutional Role:** Strong institutional data management plans and resources are essential for the data ecosystem's success. Data quality responsibility should shift more from individual users to publishers and repositories, with individual users still being accountable. Scientific publishers should enforce stricter data submission standards, avoiding accepting "data available upon request" statements.

- **Tools and Solutions:** Data analysis tools and bioinformatics pipelines should enable direct uploads to repositories with appropriate metadata. While implementation may present challenges, gradually adopting such tools would help raise standards for developers and create a more cohesive ecosystem.
- **Future Improvements:** Key recommendations included developing a guided trail for new eDNA data users, creating comprehensive data submission guides, and implementing tracking systems. The Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure was highlighted as a positive example of a national solution for eDNA data management.

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Layer 3 - Data environment - Task 3.3

Current Landscape

What we presented:

The below is what was presented.

Occurrence Related Resources

- 1) EurOBIS/EMODnet
 - a) EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology standards and external data sources and (omics) links
 - b) EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology data provider groups for data appearing in EurOBIS catalogue (data flow)
 - c) EurOBIS/EMODnet (meta)data connections with other stakeholders
- 2) OBIS
 - a) OBIS standards used; omics data links
 - b) OBIS metadata flows
 - c) OBIS cooperation/sharing
- 3) GBIF
 - a) GBIF standards used; omics data links
 - b) GBIF nodes (data provider groups)
 - c) GBIF cooperations/sharing
- 4) PANGEA
 - a) PANGEA standards used
 - b) PANGEA connections

Biobank + Voucher Related Resources

- 1) Outline of the major aspects that need to be known about
- 2) Link to the thirty-strong Biobank list
- 3) Link to questionnaire that was sent to the Biobanks

EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology standards and external data sources and (omics) links

EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology data provider groups for data appearing in EurOBIS catalogue (data flow)

EurOBIS.EMODnet (meta)data project connections

Figure 6a. Occurrence related resources - EurOBIS/EMODnet Biology.

OBIS standards used; omics data links

(Meta)Data flows to/from OBIS

OBIS cooperations - sharing metadata, coordinating standards

Figure 6b. Occurrence related resources - OBIS.

GBIF standards used; omics data links

GBIF taxonomic backbone includes all the taxonomic names GBIF deals with, starting from CoL and then adding in other authorities, and it also includes IDs for OTUs from iBOL (BINs) and UNITE (fungal); for full list of sources used, see <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d7ddbf4-2cf0-4f39-9b2a-bb099caae36c#description>

Are referenced in the Occurrence extension. Any "publication" can be given (DOI, PID, URI)

The DNA extension is a proposal of GBIF (and OBIS) and not yet ratified by TDWG, so that part does not (yet) connect to TDWG

GBIF nodes (data provider groups)

includes our stakeholders such as pangaea, dassh, OBIS nodes, PlutoF, FYI Tara Oceans, Mgnify, ENA, NCBI...

GBIF cooperations/sharing ARE THERE OTHERS?

Figure 6c. Occurrence related resources - GBIF.

Figure 6d. Occurrence related resources - PANGAEA.

Figure 7. Biobank + voucher related resources.

Major feedback and suggestions:

Some nodes are missing from the existing data landscape such as BOLD/iBOL and their connection to INSDC. (Although sequence data and a limited amount of metadata currently flow, there are plans to improve this in the future.) WISE, the EU database for freshwater aquatic data (<https://water.europa.eu/freshwater>) is another potentially missing node.

Identifying the missing links is crucial to improving connectivity across these systems. In the metadata flows of GBIF and OBIS, much of the INSDC metadata follows MixS standards, which are partially mapped to DwC. The MixS-to-DwC core mappings have been completed and documented, but the extension mappings remain a future area of focus. There is also an ongoing question about linking biobank information or BOLD specimen data, such as uploaded pictures, with genome sequence data from voucher specimens. A potential solution could be adding links in ENA/NCBI to the vouchers in BOLD or biobanks.

Regarding the information that should be portrayed, INSDC contains substantial ENVO metadata, although it is not controlled, leading to poor quality. Additionally, INSDC follows ISO 8601 for formatting collection dates.

There are two distinct strands to consider: research and national monitoring. While they do not necessarily need to be separate, it is important to acknowledge that they serve different objectives, which should be kept in mind during our work.

Several additional comments and suggestions were raised. Biobanks are a key area of interest. The genetic drift of cell cultures from biobank culture collections due to passaging over time was raised as a problem. The biobank section of T3.3 raises questions about the accessibility of biobank specimen IDs, with responses varying. For non-medical biobanks, IDs are often accessible, whereas accessibility in other contexts remains variable. A questionnaire is currently underway with thirty biobanks to assess. Persistent identifiers are particularly important when linking across repositories, ensuring that data remains traceable. Culture collections are especially significant for industrial applications.

Further investigation is needed into why the eDNA ecosystem consists of so many fragmented stakeholders. Institutions continue to create separate resources that are not interconnected, leading to additional separation across standards, taxonomy backbones, repositories, and more. If a broad definition of biobanks is adopted, the list of relevant organizations could expand significantly. One way to reach a broad range of organizations efficiently would be to engage with the DiSSCo consortium (<https://www.dissco.eu/>). Additionally, further validation of metadata fields from repositories is necessary. Another discussed suggestion involves an export function that allows datasets to be rated based on their suitability for different purposes and institutions through schema-based assessments.

EuroBIS and EMODnet have started accepting DNA-based datasets, but there are outstanding questions about the standards involved. A question was asked: what DNA-derived data can now be submitted to EurOBIS, and what criteria must be met for acceptance? Answer: The current approach allows for submitting taxa occurrence data obtained from eDNA.

Regarding GBIF, it is unlikely that mandatory fields will ever be enforced, as evaluation is left to the users. Discussions with IUCN have addressed the use of eDNA data in red-listing efforts. There is potential for the eDNAqua-Plan community to propose a list of recommended or mandatory fields, which IUCN could adopt as a requirement for data usage. GBIF already collects recommendations from various organizations, including IUCN and OBIS, but cannot assign star ratings. Instead, GBIF could provide fit-for-purpose indications. While there is some potential to include quality indicators when users download data, implementing this directly on the website would require significant resources. Additionally, different communities have varying definitions of data quality based on their specific use cases, meaning that a one-size-fits-all solution is challenging. At present, there is no quality control mechanism in place. Working on the FAIRe checklist (fair-edna.github.io) was suggested as a valuable initiative, and collaboration on this effort is ongoing. The suggestion to have different schemas to indicate what type of quality in the metadata and data are necessary to be fit for different purposes (e.g. different checklists, different EOVs, etc), mentioned above, could be an easy solution: the providers and users of data can learn if the data they are providing/using are fit for purpose simply by comparing to the schema.

For species names, certain taxonomic challenges remain. BOLD BINs and UNITE taxons rely on unranked taxonomies, where parent names are sometimes propagated to the molecular species. This does not cover all eDNA species. For instance, if a sequence is labeled as "elephant," it will appear as "elephant" in GBIF. OBIS currently accepts the taxonomy provided by users, though they plan to develop their own additional taxonomic assignment methods in the future. These may incorporate recommendations from the eDNAqua-Plan initiative. At present, OBIS aims to introduce prominent warnings regarding taxonomic assignments.

TDWG does not strictly function as a standards organization. Biodiversity archives, in general, have unique scopes and objectives, with many existing memoranda of understanding between them. Unfortunately, they remain underfunded, limiting their potential impact. Enhanced funding for resources such as OBIS and GBIF would significantly improve their ability to manage and integrate biodiversity data. The lack of funding not only affects the data itself, but also the broader scientific and management processes that rely on it. These services -- archives, taxonomic standard providers, biodiversity workflows, reference libraries -- provide critical infrastructure that should be supported as (European)(national)(international) services, because if they stop working, the science they support will stop.

In terms of metadata, there is a consensus that scientists are primarily paid to conduct research rather than to ensure FAIR data compliance. Achieving data quality requires proper funding. One suggestion is to introduce more mandatory fields for DNA data, where a "triple-star" dataset would include all the

recommended fields from initiatives like eDNAqua-Plan. If you refer to a protocol, you could use a URI pointing to Zenodo/OBPS/protocols.io etc. (but not to paid-access journals); this approach would provide the necessary context for others to assess the reliability of the data.

Mandatory fields and ranking systems are seen as essential. These requirements should be defined independently of the Darwin Core (DwC) to ensure they align with regulatory frameworks like the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). The concern is that while organizations such as OBIS, GBIF, and TDWG do valuable work, there is no guarantee of consistency in their development for management purposes. This highlights the need for independent standards that safeguard data comparability over time.

Reliability in DNA-based data identification is another key issue. This aspect should be reported in a standardised manner, but the current DwC extension may lack a dedicated field for it. Further investigation is required to determine whether updates have addressed this gap. Data managers need to know whether specific datasets are trustworthy, and this information should be captured outside of GBIF and DwC. Engagement with environmental monitoring people is encouraged. Further validation of metadata fields from the different repositories is required.

Future landscape

What we presented:

Katrina introduced a set of ideas, particularly those highlighted in orange sticky notes. The possibility of linking "products" from OBIS to EMODnet and the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) was proposed. Additionally, ODIS (Ocean Data and Information System) will establish the IOC data space (<https://www.ioc.unesco.org/en>), which does not host data itself, but links to where the data is stored. Another important note is that the ATCC genome collection is no longer freely accessible, as it has transitioned to a membership-based service (<https://genomes.atcc.org>).

In terms of specimen tracking, if the original voucher specimen—or the original lab culture from which the voucher specimen was derived—is registered in BioSamples, then all subsequent processing can be linked back to the original BioSample Accession Number. ENA also includes a relevant field in its checklist, "sample derived from", which facilitates this type of linkage. However, this would require culture collections to incorporate such metadata fields to ensure consistency and traceability.

The overarching vision involves ensuring seamless metadata integration from water sample collection through to all potential applications. Biodiversity databases should adhere to web standards, ensuring interoperability and accessibility.

Major feedback and suggestions:

A discussion on the minimum vision of success brought up several perspectives. On questioning what the baseline definition should be, the response was that at a minimum, the community should agree on templates specifying the types of metadata to be collected at each stage. LinkML could be a useful tool for this. These issues apply broadly to all data, not just aquatic data. This was acknowledged, but freshwater systems lack an equivalent of OBIS, although there is GBIF. Although freshwater databases do not currently include these standards, they could learn from and adapt marine models such as OBIS or even non-aquatic frameworks. A major challenge is demonstrating feasibility to member states, who

may hesitate due to concerns about capacity and the perceived difficulty of implementing these changes. However, showing that these methods are already feasible could help alleviate these concerns.

Ensuring FAIR data principles is essential for an ideal data landscape. It was asked whether beyond FAIR, should the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance and the TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology) Principles for digital repositories also be considered? The TRUST framework emphasises transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability, and technology, which could serve as a foundation for best practices in digital preservation. It was agreed that these are important, but that other priorities must be addressed first. Responsibility for these principles should perhaps lie with those who conducted the initial investigations.

In addition to the Nagoya Protocol, the [BBNJ Agreement \(Agreement on Marine Biodiversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction\)](#) is another relevant framework to consider. Data citations are also important, already GBIF assigns DOIs to all datasets and tracks citations, while ENA uses ORCID for contributor identification. A key challenge is ensuring that eDNA data remains accessible to biodiversity scientists who are not bioinformaticians. The question arises: who bears the responsibility for ensuring users understand the data they are accessing? Is it the data providers, creators, or users themselves?

In an ideal system, explicit information should accompany DNA-based data, clearly explaining what it represents and how it can be used. The ultimate vision is that DNA-based data is integrated into all types of decision-making processes. Automating data generation from the start would be the best approach, as this would reduce costs, improve metadata accuracy, and streamline data integration. Additionally, data from monitoring efforts has to adhere to precise data formats, which drive standardization and facilitate large-scale data use.

We agreed that all portals should do as in GBIF, and generate a DOI/URI upon a data download, that is then part of that download (not just displayed on the screen) and that points to the single or aggregation of datasets so that they can be cited. Citation of data will lead to data citations being as important as science citations. Citation tracking will only work if there are citations (DOIs/URIs) that can be cited. Journals could play a role here by having the data citations part of the metadata of the publication so it can be harvested by citation-trackers and not hidden behind a paywall.

There was a suggestion that eDNAqua-plan could create a general-purpose eDNA Data Management Plan (DMP) template. One could link that to recommendations to the marine and freshwater organisations, and perhaps to the “schema” (as suggested above) that indicate that “these (meta)data are fit for [some monitoring or scientific] purpose”.

How and By Whom Could This Be Implemented?

For the ecosystem to function optimally, all stakeholders involved should receive training in FAIR data principles. It is important to have consistent use of the concept of “standard”, and limiting the number of standards to specific data types could be more effective than attempting to cover all use cases broadly. The completeness of data is often a bigger issue than the sheer quantity of data available.

A potential solution could be modeled after platforms like iNaturalist, where many users upload photos, and the identity of organisms is confirmed collectively. A similar approach could be applied to automate data verification and integration in biodiversity and environmental monitoring systems.

Summary

During the workshop, we examined the current state of the ecosystem infrastructure and services, the linking and compatibility of aquatic biodiversity biomonitoring workflows, biobanks, and existing biodiversity databases and projects. Some aspects, such as biobanks, were limited due to pending questionnaire results; however, the types of information being sought from biobanks were outlined.

Current

For the **non-biobank landscape**, notable missing nodes include **BOLD/iBOL and WISE** (the EU database for freshwater aquatic data). A key distinction to emphasise is the two strands of eDNA: **research** and **national monitoring**, which serve different objectives and require tailored approaches. Missing links include improved metadata mapping from **INSDC** to **GBIF/OBIS** via MlxS and DwC core standards. Additionally, stronger connections are needed between biobanks and **BOLD**, particularly for specimen images and voucher information.

A recurring discussion point was the lack of **mandatory metadata fields** in most resources, coupled with **poor quality control**. These issues reduce data **FAIRness** (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and diminish the overall value of the data to the community.

For the **biobank landscape**, key biobank-relevant concepts have been identified, and over **thirty biobanks** have been contacted to provide input via a questionnaire. Initial discussions revealed that only some biobanks have **externally accessible specimen IDs**, which could impact data traceability and interoperability.

Future Vision

The presentation of ideas about the **future ideal data ecosystem** and subsequent discussions provided key insights into where to focus future efforts.

A major priority is ensuring that **all stakeholders involved in the ecosystem are trained in FAIR principles** and recognise that **generating FAIR data is a fundamental part of good science**. A central concept for the future is **reducing fragmentation** by **limiting the number of standards and repositories**, rather than having multiple institutions creating separate, disconnected infrastructures. Even well-established metadata standards require further **mapping and integration**, such as **improving DwC extension and MlxS mappings** to enhance data flow. Additionally, increasing the **amount of mandatory metadata for eDNA**, particularly through the use of **controlled vocabularies**, was highlighted as a critical step. The **FAIR checklist** may help identify priority metadata fields for standardization. Quality-control schemas indicating whether data and metadata are “fit for purpose” for different uses (e.g. IUCN, MSFD, WFD) could be implemented to make minimum sets of metadata mandatory.

Improving the metadata flow between resources is another key goal. For example, the planned **iBOL Europe** feed to **ENA (INSDC)** would strengthen data interoperability as it would have increased metadata than the current data flow of BOLD to GenBank. However, even large repositories such as **GBIF and OBIS are under-resourced**, limiting their ability to **implement quality control at scale** and fully **maximise their impact**.

A broader area for improvement lies in how **taxonomies are managed and applied**. There is a need to **increase the use of taxonomic IDs**, rather than relying solely on taxonomic names, and to implement better validation mechanisms. Currently, some repositories (**e.g., GBIF and OBIS**) **accept taxonomic data as provided by users** without additional verification, which can introduce inconsistencies.

Future opportunities include leveraging **national eco-monitoring efforts alongside research initiatives**, particularly if **appropriate metadata standards** are adopted.

For **biobanks**, a major future goal is ensuring **externally accessible biobank specimen IDs**, along with **better integration of image and other supporting data**. The results of the **biobank questionnaire** will likely reveal further **gaps and challenges**, such as **heterogeneity in metadata fields and structure**. Additionally, handling **legal, ethical, and cultural considerations**—including compliance with frameworks such as the **Nagoya Protocol** and the **BBNJ Agreement**—will be crucial in shaping future biobank data management strategies.

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Appendix 1. The virtual working space

Due to the large file size, the high-resolution export of the workshop virtual working space is added as a separate document.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

